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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

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Thermal Inactivation Kinetics of *Salmonella* Typhimurium in *Alheira* Sausage Batter

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Abstract

Alheira is a fermented sausage, typically produced in the Northern region of Portugal. These sausages are produced in a very artisanal way, mostly by small and family-run enterprises, which contributes to a product with great variability in its quality characteristics (including physicochemical, nutritional, microbiological, and sensorial). Several studies on the microbiological quality of *alheira* have detected the presence of *Salmonella* spp., which highlights the need to implement a more effective microbiological control during the production of *alheiras*, during the heat treatment phase, considering that *Salmonella* spp. showed survival in the *alheira* during maturation.

The objective of this work was to characterise the heat resistance of *Salmonella* Typhimurium (ST) in *alheira* sausage batter. Two batches of ‘*alheira*’ batter were obtained from a local producer and inoculated with an ST culture to reach $-7 \log$ CFU/g. In bags, 10 g of *alheira* batter was spread and subjected in duplicate to temperatures of 63°, 60°, 57° and 54 °C in an immersion bath, and sampled at 6 time points. A log-linear primary model fitted to each of the inactivation curves estimated the death rates of ST in *alheira* batter at 0.038 (SE=0.008), 0.126 (SE=0.003), 0.273 (SE=0.063) and 2.872 (SE=0.763) log CFU/min at 54°, 57°, 60° and 63°C, respectively, with coefficients of determination ranging from 0.914 to 0.987. Using a Bigelow model, the D value was modelled as a function of temperature, resulting in a log D* of 2.302 (SE=0.304), corresponding to 200 minutes at 50 °C to reduce ST by 1 log; and a z value of 5.016 (SE=0.839) °C. This model allows prediction of D-values and lethality times at other temperatures. For example, to achieve the log 7 reduction lethality of *Salmonella* spp. the centre of the *alheira* must be held for 9.0 seconds at 70 °C.

This study estimated for the first time the thermal kinetic parameters of a traditional Portuguese sausage, and will be useful to producers to define, control and validate thermal processes during the manufacture of *alheira* sausage.

Keywords: Raw sausage; D value; z value; log-linear death model; Bigelow.

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